

Data Placement Strategies for Owner-Compute, Multi-Accelerator Distributed Task Based Scheduling

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Asynchronous Many Tasks

- Runtime System:
 - Manages local parallelism
 - Schedules tasks on cores and on accelerators
 - Manages memory
 - Adapts the execution to the local hardware (NUMA, GPUs)
 - Stage data to accelerators
 - Moves data between nodes transparently and asynchronously

Main goal: eliminate global synchronization, reduce wait time, better resource fill

PaRSEC: naturally handles heterogeneous

Project Description:

The Parallel Runtime Scheduling and Execution Controller (**PaRSEC**) Environment provides a **task-based runtime** software component to dynamically execute fine grain tasks (tens of microsec) on heterogeneous distributed systems, and a **productivity toolbox** consisting of a development framework for building Domain Specific Languages (DSLs) and extensions, with debugging, trace collection, and analysis tools.

- **Seamlessly leverage the combined computing power of accelerators and manycore at any scale**
 - Distributed fine grain tasking is a new paradigm to access hybrid distributed systems.
 - PaRSEC is essential for the ECP software ecosystem because it enables ECP libraries (such as SLATE), programming models and apps (such as NWChemEx) to efficiently engage with a task-based programming paradigm.
- **Separation of concerns**
 - Fine grain tasking proposed by PaRSEC in a pure dataflow programming environment enables **domain scientists to focus mainly on algorithmic aspects**, and **leave the architectural details and optimization to the runtime** supporting the programming paradigm.
 - **Overlap communication/computation, data movements, load-balancing are delegated** to a shared infrastructure, thereby **improving code portability to and between ECP systems**.
- **Productivity**
 - PaRSEC supports the development of **domain-specific languages and tools to simplify and improve the productivity** when designing for, or integrating applications with PaRSEC.
 - PaRSEC supports the development of **performance and profiling tools adequate for the distributed tasking model**, which are critical to sustain a productive application development cycle.

PaRSEC: High Impact applications

IMPACT AND APPLICATIONS

Originally, PaRSEC was a tightly integrated runtime for DPLASMA, a distributed Linear Algebra Package. Now, PaRSEC and DPLASMA are separate projects. PaRSEC has evolved to support multiple user-driven scenarios, with integrations in **ScaLAPACK-API DPLASMA**, **SLATE**, **NWCHEM-EX** (PaRSEC integrated with TiledArray and MADNESS), **EXA-GEOSTAT** (PaRSEC used to perform a **Gordon-Bell Finalist** run at scale on the Fugaku system), etc.

NWCHEM: Open Source High Performance Computational Chemistry

PaRSEC is integrated with NWCHEM, notably, PaRSEC accelerates the computation of **block-sparse matrix multiplication** used to determine the steps of the **CCSD electronic structure model**. We evaluated with C65H132 which is representative of 1-D polymers and quasi-linear molecules, such as some proteins.

HIGH PERFORMANCE UNIFIED SOFTWARE FOR GEOSTATISTICS ON MANY-CORE SYSTEMS
ExaGeoStat

PaRSEC's unique feature of managing irregular datasets enables new algorithms that are either impossible to write with other runtimes, or overly complicated for users to express in the non-dataflow paradigm. In this example, the EXA-GEOSTAT application resolves **moisture/soil evaporation** problems using the PaRSEC accelerated algorithm, with tasks dynamically using compression based on **Low-Rank techniques**, and **dynamic use of mixed-precision computation**.

PaRSEC integration in the application does not require a full rewrite, it takes inputs from, and produces outputs compatible with the rest of the codebase. In this example **NWCHEM-EX hands-over data** from the GlobalArray format for use in a **PaRSEC accelerated kernel**.

- Mixed precision
- Irregular algorithms
- Sparse
- Multiple Gordon Bell runs fueled by PaRSEC
- Winning run for 2024 Gordon Bell Climate Challenge

Programming AMTs, big picture

Data Collection
Distribution: e.g.,
2D-Cyclic

Dataflow: DAG of Tasks,
obtained from a DSL

- GEQRT
- TSQRT
- UNMQR
- TSMQR

Kernels: typically
BLAS/cuBLAS/hipBLAS

What happens to your tasks?

Task Affinity to nodes (based on Data Distribution)

- GEQRT ■
- UNMQR ■
- TSQRT ■
- TSMQR ■

TASKS

Example Data Distribution:
2D Block Cyclic (3x2)

0	3	0	3	0	3
1	4	1	4	1	4
2	5	2	5	2	5
0	3	0	3	0	3
1	4	1	4	1	4
2	5	2	5	2	5

Data Distribution

- 2D cyclic data distribution
- Each process (rank) receives a set of blocks if it maps onto a 2D grid
- Local matrices are contiguous concatenations of the local blocks

	0	1	2	0
0	A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{13}	A_{14}
1	A_{21}	A_{22}	A_{23}	A_{24}
0	A_{31}	A_{32}	A_{33}	A_{34}
1	A_{41}	A_{42}	A_{43}	A_{44}

Global View

	0	1	2	
0	A_{11}	A_{14}	A_{12}	A_{13}
0	A_{31}	A_{34}	A_{32}	A_{33}
1	A_{21}	A_{24}	A_{22}	A_{23}
1	A_{41}	A_{44}	A_{42}	A_{43}

Local View

POTRF
TRSM
GEMM

Irregular Data Collections

Flexibility of data distributions: Executing on elastic data sets

- Input data not necessarily distributed according to a regular distribution.
- Example: input data is stored in a Distributed Geographical Database, and provided by a satellite scan

- Multiple approaches:
 - compute where the data is located (*owner*)
 - Compute according to the canonical 2D Cyclic data distribution (*canonical*)
 - Compute according to the closest load-balancing data distribution (*closest*)
- PaRSEC allows to implement the 3 approaches with the **unchanged QR DAG** of Tasks, simply by changing the data collection distribution

DGEQRF Time to completion

Intel Westmere-EP E5606 CPUs at 2.13GHz
10GB IB cluster

Data movements and task affinity

- Who takes care of data movement?
- When do my data get copied?
- Are there local copies?

Task Affinity to nodes (based on Data Distribution)

Proposed Placement Strategies

- On Node, dispatching between multiple GPUs
 - Allocate data on host, use UVM to automatically fetch data as needed
 - Random
 - Runtime Heuristic that enforce locality/reuse
 - Runtime Heuristic that enforce load balance
 - Runtime Heuristic Mix: favor locality, except if load balance is poor
 - User-directed
- Inter-node, dispatching RECV between multiple GPUs with GDRcopy (or similar)
 - Recv to host, dispatch later (using on-node dispatch)
 - Random
 - User-directed

Data placement and owner-compute

- Owner-compute scheduling
- Dispatch tasks to the GPU that host the data with WRITE access, **i.e. strong correlation between data placement and task placement**
- Data can be positioned on a GPU to prepare for the task that will **write to** it (it will often be **positioned on its preferred GPU**)
- Data can be pre-positioned on that GPU when it is **read**, it will be **positioned on the preferred GPU for the data written to** by the requestor task!
- Except if memory runs out, modified (written-to) data do not migrate

Details on UVM impl.

- Implemented by disabling PaRSEC data stage-in (i.e., **removing `cudaMemcpyAsync`** calls)
- Tested 3 variants
- Use **`cudaHostAlloc(Portable, WriteCombine)`**
- Use `cudaMallocManaged` with **`cudaMemAdvise(setAccessedBy)`** where `cudaMemcpyAsync` would have been called
- Use `cudaMallocManaged` with **`cudaMemAdvise(setPreferredLocation)`** where `cudaMemcpyAsync` would have been called
- *Rest of scheduling/task placement is identical to the user-directed strategy*

Detail on load-balance/reuse heuristics

- **Runtime based**: use current location of data and current load of accelerators to take decision
- **Enforce reuse strategy**: place data required by a task on the GPU that already holds task input data (maximize reuse, minimize migrating READ inputs)
- **Enforce load balance strategy**: pick the device with the best ETA: we maintain load balance information for all GPU, when considering where to place input data for a task, we choose the GPU with the best time of completion and position data on that GPU.
- **Mix**: prefer reuse, except if load balance is poor (e.g., 20% or more imbalance)

Test Applications, user-directed placement

- Expressed in Dataflow using the Parameterized Task Graph input language
- All kernel types are accelerated on GPU
 - No kernels executed on the host (mix of host-GPU computation is possible, but disabled on the test systems as that reduces performances)
- Placement expressed as advice for the blocks on the input matrices

- DPOTRF: Distributed Cholesky Factorization (LLT)
 - User-directed data placement:
 - Internode placement is 2d-cyclic
 - On-node placement between GPUs is 2d-cyclic (that is, blocks that are node local receive an advise-on-device that makes their execution prefer a specific GPU based on a 2d-cyclic organization of GPUs
 - given rank (p, q) in the 2D grid (P, Q) with $G = GP \times GQ$ GPUs; Tile $A(m, n)$ of the matrix A is set to be located on rank $(m \bmod P, n \bmod Q)$, and on GPU $Gp * GQ + Gq$, where $Gp = (m/P) \bmod GP$, and $Gq = n/Q \bmod GQ$.

- DGEMM: Distributed Matrix Multiply
 - User-directed data placement:
 - Internode placement is 2d-cyclic
 - On-node placement between GPUs is 1d-row-cyclic
 - given rank (p, q) in the 2D grid (P, Q) with G GPUs; Tile $A(m, n)$ of the matrix A is set to be located on rank $(m \bmod P, n \bmod Q)$, and on GPU g , where $g = m \bmod G$

Effect of data placement: 1 node 8 GPUs

- UVM: poor performance
- User-directed is best
- Runtime-automated strategies are all comparable

- *Skew1: always load balance*
- *Skew0: always collocate for max data reuse*
- *Default: data reuse, but load balance if more than 20% off balance*

DPOTRF Guyot, 8x A100-SXM4-80G

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DGEMM Guyot, 8x A100-SXM4-80G

Data placement: multi-node, multi-GPU

DGEMM, Summit, 6x V100-SXM2 per node

- Inter-node receptions in host memory
- Selection of target GPU when dependent tasks becomes ready
- Similar perf. Between runtime automated strategies

4 nodes, 24 V100

64 nodes, 384 V100

16 nodes, 96 V100

256 nodes, 1536 V100

Data placement: multi-node, multi-GPU

DPOTRF, Summit, 6x V100-SXM2 per node

- Inter-node receptions in host memory
- Maximum reuse strategy causes severe load imbalance
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Data placement: multi-node, multi-GPU

DPOTRF, Summit, 6x V100-SXM2 per node

256 nodes, 1536 V100

- Inter-node receptions in host memory
- Maximum reuse strategy causes severe load imbalance
- Perf. Difference between runtime-directed and user-directed increases with problem size!
- *Skew1: always load balance*
- *Skew0: always collocate for max data reuse*
- *Default: data reuse, but load balance if more than 20% off balance*

Summit vs Frontier: why receiving to GPUs

SUMMIT

FRONTIER

Effect of placement: reception buffers in GPU

- Receiving to host on Frontier is a disaster
- Cross-traffic reduces available bandwidth
- Diff. between random and user-directed placement is low

DPOTRF Frontier, 8x MI250X, 2 GCD/rank, 4 ranks per node
Strong Scaling N=131,072

Effect of placement: reception buffers in GPU

DPOTRF Frontier, 8x MI250X, 2 GCD/rank, 4 ranks per node
Weak Scaling N=131,072 (4 nodes, 32 GCDs)
to N=327,680 (32 nodes, 256 GCDs)

- Weak scaling
- Perf. Difference between random and user-directed placement insignificant

Related Works

- **Cloud and workflows**

- Chunlin L., Qianqian C., and Youlong L. Optimal data placement strategy considering capacity limitation and load balancing in geographically distributed cloud. *FGCS*, 127:142–159, 2022.
- Q. Sun, M. Romanus, T. Jin, H. Yu, P. Bremer, S. Petruzza, S. Klasky, and M. Parashar. In-staging data placement for asynchronous coupling of task-based scientific workflows. In *ESPM2*, pages 2–9, 2016.

- **Task scheduling heuristics**

- J. Lifflander, P. Pebay, N. Slattengren, P. Pebay, R. Pfeiffer, J. Kotulski, and S. McGovern. A communication- and memory-aware model for load balancing tasks. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2404.16793>, 2024.
- M. Gonthier, L. Marchal, and S. Thibault. Memory-aware scheduling of tasks sharing data on multiple GPUs with dynamic runtime systems. In *IPDPS*, pages 694–704, May 2022.

- **User-tuned distributions**

- Q. Cao, G. Bosilca, W. Wu, D. Zhong, A. Bouteiller, and J. Dongarra. Flexible data redistribution in a task-based runtime system. In *2020 IEEE CLUSTER*, pages 221–225, Sep. 2020.
- T. Cojean, A. Guermouche, A. Hugo, R. Namyst, and P.A. Wacrenier. Resource aggregation for task-based cholesky factorization on top of modern architectures. *Parallel Computing*, 83:73–92, 2019.
- G. Kwasniewski, M. Kabić, M. Besta, J. VandeVondele, et al. Red-blue pebbling revisited: near optimal parallel matrix-matrix multiplication. *SC '19*, 2019.
- P. Anastasiadis, N. Papadopoulou, N. Koziris, and G. Goumas. Uncut-GEMMs: Communication-aware matrix multiplication on multi-GPU nodes. In *CLUSTER*, pages 143–154, Sep. 2024.

In Conclusion

- Correct data placement is critical for performance (duh)
- Very naïve placement (i.e., using UVM) has poor performance and is not a realistic option, even with cudaMemAdvise at the right places
- Diff. between runtime heuristics often small
- Yet, On-the-surface reasonable heuristics can fall flat on their face (e.g., always favor data reuse), beware
- User-directed placement still valuable, gains can be significant
- Future works: How effective user-directed in more irregular apps? Can runtime heuristics close the gap, win?
- Future works: AI heuristics? AI assisted user-defined placement?